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Asadullayeva Nurana Firudin

PhD in Philology,

National Azerbaijan Literature Museum named after Nizami Ganjavi, Azerbaijan

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INFLUENCE OF SOVIET IDEOLOGY ON LITERATURE

Abstract.

In the 1920s and 1930s, in Soviet literature, including Azerbaijani Soviet literature, which is a part of this literature, criticism and theoretical-aesthetic reality were promoted as the primary principles of socialist realism; in those years, this concept was understood as a description of reality from the point of view of the interests of the proletariat. In relation to literature and the art of words, not artistry, but ideological directions and tendencies prevailed, and humanism was denied. The approach to the description of reality, which required such a special "Bolshevik authenticity", determined the strict framework of literature and allowed Bolshevik critics to call the works that reflect life in its real reality a slander against the Soviet authorities, and to attribute their authors to the enemies of the people.

The defense of the principles of the socialist realism method in the 1950s and 1960s meant that these principles, defined in the 1930s, were still valid. Here, the defense of the idea of national form and socialist culture in content was nothing more than living those theoretical principles in new conditions. With this, the ideological center aimed to give more socialist content to the strengthened national idea at the new stage. The events that took place in the center - in Moscow - immediately manifested themselves in places. As a result of the establishment and strengthening of the Soviet power in Azerbaijan in the 20s of the 20th century, a unique ideological literature and literary studies emerged here. However, this ideological mechanism formed under the name of "socialist realism" began to show clearly noticeable cracks from the 1960s.

Keywords: literature, Soviet ideology, socialist realism, literary criticism, Isa Huseynov

Introduction. The Communist-Bolshevik party, well aware of the important influence of fiction on the public consciousness, tried to create a mechanism of strict control over poets and writers in order to use it as an ideological tool. In the 1920s, various literary and artistic organizations were created for this purpose. In order to fully control all literary processes, in 1934 all literary organizations were abolished, and in their place a single body called the Union of Soviet Writers was created, which had its own branches in each allied republic. According to the method called "socialist realism", formalized at the Congress of the Union of Writers, Soviet writers had to fight internal and external enemies with their pens.

The method of socialist realism as an ideological tool. Armed with the methodology of socialist realism, the literature of the 1930s and 1940s always reflected the unbreakable relationship between the positive hero and the collective. It was believed that the collective always has a positive effect on the formation of the personality, forms will and character in the hero. The main area where the positive hero had to put his strength was creative work. It was thought that as a result of such labor, not only material values are created and the power of the workers and peasants is strengthened, but also true people and patriots grow.

In Soviet literature and art, the cult of the hero, the true man, is combined with the cult of the leader. Lenin and Stalin, as well as their lower-level leaders (Dzerzhinsky, Kirov, Parkhomenko, Chapayev, etc.) were created and distributed in millions of copies in artistic prose, poetry, drama, music, cinema, and visual arts. Lenin's praise can be found in the works of almost all

prominent Soviet writers, including the works of S. Yesenin, B. Pasternak, and R. Rza. Even folk storytellers and lovers told stories and sang songs about Lenin and Stalin. "A retrospective look at the historical-literary process allows us to understand that the canonization, mythification, and heroization of leaders are included in the genetic code of Soviet literature. Without the image of the leader (leaders), our literature has not existed at all for seventy years, and this, of course, is not accidental." (7, 3).

Of course, not all poets and writers could get used to socialist principles. Some of them were subjected to repressions, and some of them turned to historical topics to save their lives from repressions. There were victims of repression in all republics of the Soviet Union. At first, they intimidated them by criticizing them, and then turned to open threats. For example, in the March 17, 1937 issue of "Communist" newspaper, critic Seyfulla Shamilov wrote about the poet Mikayil Mushfiq: "Mushfiq should know that the revolution will not allow compromise on any issue... they can roll into the abyss with the enemies (5, 3).

Most of the works written on historical subjects (M. Zoshenko's "Kolensky" and "Taras Shevchenko", M. S. Ordubadi's "Sword and Pen" novels, etc.) were adapted to modern requirements and history was reflected in the spirit of socialist realism.

The war of 1941-1945 brought great suffering to the people, but at the same time it somewhat weakened the ideological pressure. Because, hardened as a result of the battles, the Soviet people began to feel a little free. The victory, which cost a lot of money, created enthusiasm among the people. At that time, many books written about the war reflect the truths of life

quite accurately. Of course, their authors could not be completely free from ideological stereotypes, but in any case, what they wrote was closer to the truth than in the pre-war period.

Stalin, who had long since become an absolutist dictator, could not tolerate the formation of cracks in the monolith of consensus. The leader decided that it was impossible to retreat from the "line of unanimity" that had cost so much energy and resources, and therefore a new wave of repression on the ideological front began in the second half of the 1940s. Famous decisions are made about the magazines "Zvezda" ("Star") and "Leningrad", and the works of Akhmatova and Zoshenka are subjected to gross distortions and insults. (6, 587-591).

Along with this, the artists who carefully followed the rules of the game were awarded, they were given orders and honorary titles. But sometimes even faithful service did not guarantee safety. This can be seen more clearly in the example of A. Fadeyev, who was considered the first person of Soviet literature and became the general secretary of the Union of Writers of the USSR. In 1945, his novel "The Young Guard" was published. A. Fadeyev described the patriotism of teenage boys and girls who remained in the occupied territories during the war and their struggle against the invaders. The romantic lines in the work were intended to further enhance the heroism of young people. One would think that the party should have welcomed the appearance of such a work. After all, Fadeyev was brought up in the spirit of communism and created a wreath of characters who proved his loyalty to the wills of his fathers by his deeds. However, Stalin decided to start a new campaign to tighten the demands even more, and in one of his speeches, he mentioned Fadeyev as a writer who made a mistake. After that, an article about the novel "Young Guard" was published in the "Pravda" newspaper, an organ of the Central Committee. The article indicated that the role of the party in the secret activities of the youth was not sufficiently covered and thus the real situation was distorted (9, 294). Fadeyev reacted to this as it should, and published a new edition of the novel in 1951. Contrary to the facts of life, the leading role of the party was greatly exaggerated in the new editorial office. But the writer knew what he was doing. In one of his personal letters addressed to Y. N. Libedinsky in 1948, he jokingly, and in some sense ironically, wrote: "I am still turning the young guard into the old guard and, taking into account the known weaknesses of my nature, I avoid public life." (10, 247).

As a result, Soviet writers were forced to adapt every detail of their work to the requirements of socialist realism. In literature (P. Pavlenko's "Happiness", S. Babayevski's "Golden Star Cavalry", M. Husayn's "Absheron" novels, etc.) and other types of art, the motto "happy life in a free and fertile land" begins to be sung. At the same time, the owner of this happy life does not feel himself as a valuable and comprehensive personality, but as a small part of a work, a production that stands above the personality" (8, 314).

It is not surprising that the "production" novel, which originated in the 1920s, became one of the most widespread genres in the 1950s. The names of the

works already characterize their content and direction (V. Popov's "Steel and Slag", V. Kojevnikov's "Living Water", M. Husayn's "Black Stones" novels, etc.). Against the backdrop of bridge building, metal smelting, and harvesting, human feelings seemed secondary. The participants of the novel "Production" were visible only within the boundaries of the factory, workshop, coal mine, collective farm area, outside of this framework it was not worth talking about them.

Writers who describe life in "revolutionary development", which is constantly improving according to party slogans, do not touch the dark side of life at all. The intended works are immediately successfully carried out by the heroes, any difficulties are also eliminated. The works of poets and writers who described the problems more prominently from this aspect were awarded the Stalin Prize. The theorists of socialist realism also immediately began to justify the necessity of this kind of optimistic art. One of them wrote about it like this: "We need holiday literature: "not literature about holidays, but holiday literature that lifts people above trifles and coincidences" (11, 184).

The writers were able to sensitively capture the "demands of the times". Daily domestic life was hardly covered in Soviet literature, because Soviet people had to stand above domestic trifles. Even if daily household life was touched upon, it was done in order to remove the temporary difficulties of the real person, to demonstrate more clearly the selfless work for the common good.

Such an understanding of the tasks facing literature and art in itself led to the creation of the "non-conflict theory". Although such a view of literature did not last for a long time, this situation clearly showed the essence of Soviet literature in the 50s. The essence of this theory was as follows: class contradictions in the USSR have already been eliminated. Therefore, there is no reason for the emergence of dramatic conflicts, only the struggle of "good" with "better" can be discussed. If public interests were the first priority in the Soviet country, there was nothing left for the author but to write about the "production process".

Description of socio-political processes. The principles of the socialist realism method were still valid in the literature of the 1950s and 1960s. On December 4-5, 1957, a republican meeting of literature and art activists was held in Azerbaijan based on N. Khrushov's article "For the close connection of literature and art with people's life". The meeting was attended by party and state officials, as well as heads of creative organizations. Here, writer Isa Huseynov's short story "Burning Heart" was discussed, and it was specially mentioned that the writer described the image of the first secretary in this work in a dull way, and this point was criticized. The Chairman of the Board of the Writers' Union, Suleyman Rahimov, also devoted space to this work in his speech and noted that the author described "the negative aspects of life by weakly showing them" (4, 8).

Literature and art, under the control of the political system, still considered the description of modern life events from an ideological point of view under the name of nationalism and attachment to the people's life,

and opposed socialist realism to the world literary scale. The cliché of socialist realism was one of the most important tools for writers in the hands of literary criticism. If there was an idea or an idea in any work that did not correspond to the requirements of the political system, criticism immediately came into play. For a writer, creator (poet, artist, composer, etc.), following the directives of party congresses was considered one of the main duties.

In the late 1950s and early 1960s, writer Isa Huseynov wrote several prose works dealing with social problems. He tried to analyze the socio-political processes in the works "Burning Heart" (1957), "Telegram" (1961), "Nightmare" (1963). For the first time, these works, which repeated or continued each other in terms of theme and conflict, did not reflect an unequivocal approach to the communist image. In other words, the period and time had already changed; Now the writer was no longer required to create positive revolutionary images, as in the 30s. Now, in the presentation of images, positive and negative poles are more preferred, however, the image of a communist or a statesman was not presented in a negative way. In this sense, the attitude of literary criticism to these works of I. Huseynov was ambiguous. They even accused the writer of slandering the Soviet society. The writer Mehdi Huseyin commented on the unfair criticism of Isa Huseynov in his report at the 3rd congress of the Azerbaijan Writers' Union and said: "Some accused him of making wrong generalizations by portraying the secretary of the Raykom as a negative image, and others accused him of slandering the existence of the Soviet Union. One of the critics even claimed that I. Huseynov, when describing the secretary of the raykom as Sultan Amirli, created a wrong idea about the party work in the region" (1, 38). It is clear from this that the current literary criticism played the role of "prosecutor" against the writer's works and tried to evaluate his creativity ideologically. It should also be taken into account that I. Huseynov was taking his first steps as a young writer at that time, and such criticisms did not remain unaffected by his work. As a result of this, the writer has reworked the works "Burning Heart", "Nightmare" and "Telegram" and published them under the name "Burning Heart". The main issue here was the conflicting points in the creation of the image of the statesman, that is, Sultan Amirli, the first secretary of the region. Until then, the images of a communist or the secretary of the Raikom were shown positively in the literature. All these were important factors for the formation of a young writer. The main reason for M. Huseyn's defense of the writer was that criticism did not lead to administrative penalties for the writer. In the novel, the writer raised the issue of the relationship between the leader and the people and created a convincing image of Sultan Amirli. This meant leaving the framework of socialist realism. Here, the writer also described Sultan Amirli as a leader in the region who was arrogant and self-satisfied. Criticism reminds Isa Huseynov that he has not yet properly understood life as a Soviet writer, they say that the "dangerous people" depicted in his works "Native and Stranger" and "Burning Heart" are not so powerful and majestic in real life as to evoke an

impression of invincibility. Criticism, after noting positive images of collective farmers as a positive aspect of the work, also pointed out its shortcomings. In the comments to the work, it was noted that the writer did not see the flaws in life well, did not evaluate them correctly, and did not show the right way to eliminate them. Of course, what was required of the writer included only the task of criticizing socialist realism. Most importantly, it was concluded that the public position and purpose of the writer was not clear.

In the novel, I. Huseynov managed to describe life with all its contradictions, not one-sided. It all starts when Sultan Amirli's nephew Samad Amirli returns to the district after graduating from the party school and observes the events here. Sultan Amirli has nothing to say here, because he is the head of the district and also the most powerful authority. His strength is measured by the names he made during the war and his amirship. But now, a long time has passed since the war, and since everything has changed, it is impossible to control the people with the previous methods and methods. His nephew Samad Amirli was the first to see and understand this. When he told his uncle about it, it became clear that Sultan Amirli himself knows and understands this situation well. In his conversation with Samad Amirli, he says: "No personal initiative! They are looking for "comrade Amirli" as soon as they get a little narrow. You don't know, brother, how humiliated I am among them!" (3, 78).

The true picture of the social life of the time was artistically expressed in the writer's works "Nightmare", "Native and Strangers", "Telegram", "Kollu Kokha", "Burning Heart", etc. However, since this innovation caused some concern among critics and some party functionaries, they reacted to it from an ideological position. Researcher Akif Aliyev summarized the attacks on the writer in these years and came to the following correct conclusion: "With this, the debates about the work of Isa Huseynov began. The main issue in these disputes was not whether the writer's search was successful or not. It was supposedly about the writer's complete departure from national traditions. Of course, criticism was not the only culprit here. There were difficulties in suddenly realizing life changes" (2, 126).

Result. From the beginning of the 1960s, the "non-conflict theory" began to be slowly forgotten, because ordinary readers already understood that the "holiday literature" was completely separated from reality. The condemnation of the "personality cult" at the 20th Congress of the Communist Party of the Soviet Union held in 1956 led to a softening of the political course in other domestic areas as well. The new generation of writers, who did not see the strict Stalinist school, began to write works in a new style on new topics that did not correspond to the principles of socialist realism in the new situation. In literary criticism, the concept of socialist realism gradually begins to weaken. It becomes clear that any phenomenon of modern literature can be described without taking into account the principles of socialist realism. Thus, socialist realism was born at the behest of a totalitarian system, and it served this system faithfully for a long time. As soon as the

party weakened the struggle a little, it began to disintegrate, and after the collapse of the political system, it completely disappeared into the archives of history.

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